

Machine learning discoveries of BLM-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Bloom syndrome/BLM RecQ like helicase (BLM) is a gene, mutations in which causes a rare autosomal recessive genetic disorder called Bloom syndrome. This is characterized by predisposition to the development of cancer, short stature, and genomic instability. RecQ like helicase is a family of helicase enzymes or motor proteins that drive the unwinding of paired DNA by moving directionally along a nucleotidic backbone in the 3' to 5' direction, thus separating two hybridized nucleic acid strands using energy from ATP hydrolysis. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, BLM was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of BLM-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2nd order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which BLM-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of BLM with members of BRCA DNA repair associated (BRCA), DNA topoisomerase (TOP), RecQ mediated genome instability (RMI), DNA replication helicase/nuclease 2 (DNA2), budding uninhibited by benzimidazoles mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase (BUB), cyclin dependent kinase (CDK), polo like kinase (PLK), Fanconi anemia complementation group (FANC), heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein (HNRNP), minichromosome maintenance complex component (MCM), poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP), DNA polymerase (POL), DNA-dependent RNA polymerase (POLR), ubiquitin specific peptidase (USP) and structural maintenance of chromosomes (SMC) family.

Keywords: BLM, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning, Colorectal cancer.

^{*}ML discoveries of BLM-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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1. Introduction

1.1. BLM

BLM encodes a protein containing seven motifs which are conserved in DNA and RNA helicases. Karow et al. [1] show that the ATPase activity of recombinant BLM protein is stimulated by either single- or double- stranded DNA and BLM exhibits ATP- and Mg^{2+} - dependent DNA helicase activity that displays 3'-5' directionality. The crystal structure of BLM, as investigated by Newman et al. [2] show a nucleotide-dependent interaction of the core helicase domain with the conserved helicase and RNase D C-terminal (HRDC) domain. BLM known to unwind DNA secondary structures such as G-quadruplexes (G4s) and Danino et al. [3] demonstrate that BLM is recruited to stress granules (SGs) and is enriched in SGs upon different stress conditions and in an RNA G-quadruplexes (rG4)- dependent manner. Further, they show that BLM unwinds rG4s (as it unwinds DNA secondary structure G4) and acts as a negative regulator of SG formation. BLM is a genome stabilizer involved in the regulation of DNA replication and recombination. Mutations in the BLM gene cause genomic instability, premature aging, predisposition to cancer, immunodeficiency, and pulmonary diseases. These point to BLM being a tumor suppressor. However, Kaur et al. [4] also suggest that BLM is a proto-oncogene as it undergoes various types of alterations including increase in the transcript, copy number, and protein levels in multiple types of cancers. In multiple myeloma (MM) cells, Ovejero et al. [5] show that treatment with melphalan produced DNA damage. MM cells where BLM was overexpressed, could cope with the drug-induced DNA damage and survive the treatment, thus showing resistance. However, BLM inhibition in combination with melphalan increased DNA damage in such a way that these cells could not efficiently repair, thus leading to cell cycle arrest and cell death, and further overcame melphalan resistance. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, BLM was found to be down regulated along with other genes. Some combinations of BLM have been confirmed in wet lab, however, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [6], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [7]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [8] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. BLM related synergies

2.1.1. BLM - BRCA

Tsukada et al. [9] show that BLM and BRCA1-BARD1 coordinate mechanisms of joint DNA molecule resolution and combined deficiency in BLM and BRCA1-BARD1 (but not BRCA2) is synthetically lethal. They identify a negative genetic interaction between BLM loss and deficiency in the BRCA1-BARD1 tumor suppressor complex. Consequently, cells with defective BLM and BRCA1-BARD1 accumulate catastrophic levels of chromosome breakage and micronucleation, leading to cell death. Finally, Wu et al. [10] have demonstrated that BRCA1 forms a heterodimeric complex with BARD1, and both proteins depend on each other for mutual stability. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, BRCA family members, BARD1, and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these BRCA members and BARD1 along with BLM.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of BRCA members/BARD1 w.r.t BLM. BRCA1 - BLM shows low ranking of 289 (linear) and 376 (rbf). BRCA2 - BLM shows low ranking of 344 (linear) and 484 (rbf). BARD1 - BLM shows low ranking of 1085 (laplace) and 1136 (linear). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. Important to note is that BRCA2 also showed synergy with BLM in colorectal cancer, as its combination was assigned a low valued rank for ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer.

RANKING BRCA FAMILY/BARD1 VS BLM			
RANKING OF BRCA FAMILY/BARD1 W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
BRCA1 - BLM	1807	289	376
BRCA2 - BLM	1770	344	484
BARD1 - BLM	1085	1136	1801

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS BRCA members/BARD1.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - ● BRCA members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > BRCA-1/2 and ● BARD1 w.r.t BLM with BLM – > BARD1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
BRCA members/BARD1 w.r.t BLM	
BRCA-1/2	BLM
BARD1	BLM

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and BRCA members.

2.1.2. BLM - TOP/RMI

DNA resection is a process in which the nucleolytic processing of broken DNA ends happen as a first step of homologous recombination. This resection is orchestrated by a multienzyme complex that comprises of BLM, DNA2 and additional DNA-binding proteins. Using single-molecule imaging, Soniat et al. [11] show that BLM partners with TOP3A-RMI1/2 to form the BLM-TOP3A-RMI1/2 (BTRR) complex and determined that TOP3A-RMI1/2 aids BLM in initiating DNA unwinding, and along with MRE11-RAD50-NBS1 (MRN) complex, stimulates DNA2-mediated resection. Thus a synergy exists among these factors. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, TOP/RMI family members, DNA2, and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these TOP/RMI members and DNA2 along with BLM.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of TOP-RMI members/BARD1 w.r.t BLM. TOP2A - BLM shows low ranking of 206 (linear) and 366 (rbf). RMI1 - BLM shows low ranking of 133 (laplace) and 994 (linear). RMI2 - BLM shows low ranking of 185 (linear) and 12 (rbf). DNA2 - BLM shows low ranking of 596 (linear) and 566 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. Note that RMI-1/2 and DNA2 appear to show synergy in line with what has been established in the reference above. TOP2A was the only member of TOP family which showed synergy with BLM. The data do not contain recordings of TOP3A.

Further, TOP2B, TOPBP1 and TOP1MT showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with BLM, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • TOP-RMI members w.r.t BLM with BLM - > TOP2A and BLM - > RMI-1/2 and • DNA2 w.r.t BLM with BLM - > DNA2.

2.1.3. BLM - BUB

Telomeres and telomere-binding proteins form nucleoprotein structures to maintain genome integrity but can present serious challenges during telomere DNA replication. Li et al. [12] show that the BUB3-BUB1 complex, a component in SAC, binds to telom-

RANKING TOP-RMI FAMILY/DNA2 VS BLM			
RANKING OF TOP-RMI FAMILY/DNA2 w.r.t BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
TOP2B - BLM	829	1582	1735
TOPBP1 - BLM	1658	1638	2351
TOP2A - BLM	1659	206	366
TOP1MT - BLM	2513	2414	934
RMI1 - BLM	133	994	1582
RMI2 - BLM	1977	185	12
DNA2 - BLM	2396	596	566

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS TOP-RMI members/BARD1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
TOP-RMI members/DNA2 w.r.t BLM	
TOP2A	BLM
RMI-1/2	BLM
DNA2	BLM

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and TOP-RMI members.

eres during S phase and promotes telomere DNA replication, and demonstrate that the telomere-binding ability of BUB3 and kinase activity of BUB1, are indispensable to BUB3-BUB1 function at telomeres. They observe that TRF2 targets BUB1-BUB3 to telomeres, and BUB1 directly phosphorylates TRF1 and promotes TRF1 recruitment of BLM helicase to overcome replication stress. Thus there exists a synergy between BUB family and BLM. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, BUB family members, and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these BUB members along with BLM.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of BUB members w.r.t BLM. BUB3 - BLM shows low ranking of 1070 (laplace) and 731 (rbf). BUB1B - BLM shows low ranking of 67 (linear) and 469 (rbf). BUB1 - BLM shows low ranking of 156 (linear) and 412 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been

down regulated after the drug treatment. Note that BUB-1/3 appear to show synergy in line with what has been established in the reference above. Apart from that BUB1B also shows synergy.

RANKING BUB FAMILY VS BLM

RANKING OF BUB FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
BUB3 - BLM	1070	2180	731
BUB1B - BLM	1894	67	469
BUB1 - BLM	2718	156	412

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS BUB members/BARD1.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • BUB members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > BUB-3/1/1B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

BUB members w.r.t BLM

BUB-3/1/1B

BLM

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and BUB members.

2.1.4. BLM - CDK/PLK

As seen earlier, BLM helicase functions with TOP3A and RMI-1/2 (BTR complex) to dissolve recombination intermediates and avoid somatic crossing-over. Balbo Pogliano et al. [13] show that crossover avoidance by BTR requires the activity of cyclin-dependent kinase-1 (CDK1), Polo-like kinase-1 (PLK1), and the DDR mediator protein TOPBP1. They observe that CDK1 phosphorylates BLM and TOPBP1 and promotes the interaction of both proteins with PLK1. This stimulates the dissolution of topologically linked DNA intermediates by BLM-TOP3A. However, in our about analysis we found that the engine did not rank the combination of TOPBP1-BLM appropriately, as it showed higher ranks meaning no synergistic affect in colorectal cancer before the treatment with ETC-1922159. Nevertheless, in colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, CDK-PLK family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these CDK-PLK members along with BLM.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of CDK-PLK members w.r.t BLM. CDK20 - BLM shows low ranking of 854 (laplace), 1168 (linear) and 906 (rbf). CDK1 - BLM shows low ranking of 223 (linear) and 327 (rbf). PLK1 - BLM shows low ranking of 507 (linear) and 532 (rbf). PLK4 - BLM shows low ranking of 23 (linear) and 189 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CDK4 and CDK6 showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

RANKING CDK-PLK FAMILY VS BLM			
RANKING OF CDK-PLK FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDK20 - BLM	854	1168	906
CDK4 - BLM	1840	1457	1577
CDK6 - BLM	1858	1315	1707
CDK1 - BLM	2375	223	327
PLK1 - BLM	1753	507	532
PLK4 - BLM	2394	23	189

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS CDK-PLK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • CDK members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > CDK-20/1 and • PLK members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > PLK-1/4.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
CDK members w.r.t BLM	
CDK-20/1	BLM
PLK members w.r.t BLM	
PLK-1/4	BLM

Table 8: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and CDK-PLK members.

2.1.5. BLM - FANC

Fanconi anaemia (FA) and Bloom syndrome are autosomal recessive diseases characterised by chromosome fragility and cancer proneness. Pichierri et al. [14] provide evidence that BLM and FANCD2 colocalise and co-immunoprecipitate in response to crosslinked DNA and stalled replication forks. They also found that the FA core complex phosphorylated BLM and its assembly in nuclear foci in response to crosslinked DNA. Lansdorp and van Wietmarschen [15] in their review indicate that FANCD2 maintains epigenetic stability in tandem with the BLM helicase and acts on Guanine quadruplex (G4) DNA structures. The collapse of stalled replication forks drives genomic instability. Several mechanisms exist to resolve the subsequent replication stress. Cancer cells that use Alternative Lengthening of Telomeres (ALT) show higher levels of telomere-specific replication stress, and co-opt stalled replication forks as substrates for break-induced telomere synthesis. FANCM forms independent interactions with the BLM-TOP3A-RMI (BTR) complex and the FA core complex. Lu et al. [16] demonstrate that FANCM depletion incites ALT activity and FANCM-mediated attenuation of ALT demands its inherent DNA translocase activity and interaction with the BTR complex, but does not require the FA core complex. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, FANC family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FANC members along with BLM.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9. The table 9 shows rankings of FANC members w.r.t BLM. FANCB - BLM shows low ranking of 957 (laplace), 246 (linear) and 261 (rbf). FANCI - BLM shows low ranking of 1081 (linear) and 1472 (rbf). FANCM - BLM shows low ranking of 535 (linear) and 668 (rbf). FANCD2 - BLM shows low ranking of 38 (linear) and 78 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FANCG, FANCF and FANCD2OS showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - • FANC members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > FANC-B/I/M/D2.

2.1.6. BLM - HNRNP

DNA double-strand break (DSB) signaling and repair are crucial for cell viability. Polo et al. [17] show that HNRNPUL-1/2 play important roles in cellular responses to DSBs as they act as binding partners for the DSB sensor complex MRE11-RAD50-NBS1 (MRN). Further, they establish that HNRNPUL-1/2 function downstream of MRN and CtBP-interacting protein (CtIP) to promote recruitment of the BLM helicase to DNA breaks. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, HNRNP family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these HNRNP members along with BLM.

RANKING FANC FAMILY VS BLM			
RANKING OF FANC FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FANCD2OS - BLM	336	2152	1965
FANCB - BLM	957	246	261
FANCI - BLM	1825	1081	1472
FANCM - BLM	1943	535	668
FANCG - BLM	2438	2718	607
FANCF - BLM	2478	2031	2544
FANCD2 - BLM	2716	38	78

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS FANC members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FANC members w.r.t BLM	
FANC-B/I/M/D2	BLM

Table 10: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and FANC members.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11. The table 11 shows rankings of HNRNP members w.r.t BLM. HNRNPC - BLM shows low ranking of 379 (laplace) and 1269 (linear). HNRNPR - BLM shows low ranking of 391 (laplace) and 1349 (linear). HNRNPA0 - BLM shows low ranking of 1141 (laplace) and 1353 (linear). HNRNPA1L2 - BLM shows low ranking of 1255 (laplace) and 982 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HNRNPA3, HNRNPD, HNRNPM, HNRNPH3 and HNRNPA1 showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • HNRNP members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > HNRNP-C/R/A0/A1L2.

RANKING HNRNP FAMILY VS BLM			
RANKING OF HNRNP FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HNRNPA3 - BLM	84	1786	2724
HNRNPD - BLM	138	1782	2576
HNRNPM - BLM	170	2514	2448
HNRNPC - BLM	379	1269	2427
HNRNPR - BLM	391	1349	2487
HNRNPA0 - BLM	1141	1353	2041
HNRNPA1L2 - BLM	1255	2518	982
HNRNPH3 - BLM	1774	2709	2458
HNRNPA1 - BLM	1957	733	1854

Table 11: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between BLM VS HNRNP members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HNRNP members w.r.t BLM	
HNRNP-C/R/A0/A1L2	BLM

Table 12: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and HNRNP members.

2.1.7. BLM - MCM

Shastri et al. [18] analyzed the composition of the BLM complex during unperturbed S-phase and found a direct physical interaction with the MCM6 via N-terminal domain of MCM6 in G1 phase and C-terminal CDT1-binding domain of MCM6 in S-phase, with a third site playing a role for MCM6 binding after DNA damage. They observed that disruption of MCM6 binding to BLM in S-phase lead to supra-normal DNA replication speed in unperturbed cells. Further, disruption of BLM-MCM6 interaction lead to delay in repair of replication-dependent DNA double-strand breaks, with cells becoming hypersensitive to DNA damage and replication stress. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, MCM family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order

combination of these MCM members along with BLM.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of MCM members w.r.t BLM. MCM6 - BLM shows low ranking of 57 (linear) and 150 (rbf). MCM10 - BLM shows low ranking of 5 (linear) and 110 (rbf). MCMDC2 - BLM shows low ranking of 1352 (linear) and 1143 (rbf). MCM5 - BLM shows low ranking of 33 (linear) and 182 (rbf). MCM4 - BLM shows low ranking of 312 (linear) and 16 (rbf). MCM2 - BLM shows low ranking of 175 (linear) and 500 (rbf). MCM3 - BLM shows low ranking of 113 (linear) and 34 (rbf). MCM7 - BLM shows low ranking of 22 (linear) and 120 (rbf). MCM8 - BLM shows low ranking of 14 (linear) and 155 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING MCM FAMILY VS BLM

	laplace	linear	rbf
MCM6 - BLM	1787	57	150
MCM10 - BLM	2064	5	110
MCMDC2 - BLM	2142	1352	1143
MCM5 - BLM	2419	33	182
MCM4 - BLM	2433	312	16
MCM2 - BLM	2458	175	500
MCM3 - BLM	2535	113	34
MCM7 - BLM	2550	22	120
MCM8 - BLM	2734	14	155

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS MCM members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - ● MCM members w.r.t BLM with BLM → MCM-6/10/DC2/5/4/2/3/7/8.

2.1.8. BLM - PARP

Telomeres are nucleoprotein structures at eukaryotic chromosome termini. Telomere repeat binding factor 1 (TRF1) binds telomere duplex and assists DNA replication.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

MCM members w.r.t BLM
MCM-6/10/DC2/5/4/2/3/7/8 BLM

Table 14: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and MCM members.

Maresca et al. [19] found that PARP1 PARylates TRF1 in S-phase through direct interaction, in order to dissociate it from telomere duplex, thus allowing replication fork opening. Further, TRF1-PARP1 complex recruits WRN and BLM helicases on the G-rich strand to resolve secondary structures, thus allowing for replication fork progression. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, PARP family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these PARP members along with BLM.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of PARP members w.r.t BLM. PARP2 - BLM shows low ranking of 768 (linear) and 1397 (rbf). PARPBP - BLM shows low ranking of 191 (linear) and 56 (rbf). PARP1 - BLM shows low ranking of 94 (linear) and 187 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, PARP16 showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

RANKING PARP FAMILY VS BLM

RANKING OF PARP FAMILY W.R.T BLM

	laplace	linear	rbf
PARP16 - BLM	337	1642	1839
PARP2 - BLM	1027	768	1397
PARPBP - BLM	2251	191	56
PARP1 - BLM	2643	94	187

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between BLM VS PARP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - ● PARP members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > PARP-2/BP/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

PARP members w.r.t BLM	
PARP-2/BP/1	BLM

Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and PARP members.

2.1.9. BLM - POL / POLR

Transcriptionally active loci are prone to breakage and evidence shows that DNA Double-Strand Breaks (DSB) arising in active genes are handled by Transcription-Coupled DSB Repair (TC-DSBR) pathway. In TC-DSBR in human cells, Cohen et al. [20] discovered that BLM is recruited in a transcription dependent-manner at DSBs where it nurtures resection, RAD51 binding and accurate Homologous Recombination repair. They report that during DSB repair, RNA:DNA hybrids are highly toxic intermediates that initiate BLM-POLD3-dependent pathway which triggers cell death. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, POL family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these POL members along with BLM. Additionally, I also tabulate combinations of POLR-BLM to see if there exists plausible synergy between DNA-dependent RNA polymerase and BLM.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of POL members w.r.t BLM. POLA2 - BLM shows low ranking of 759 (laplace), 1175 (linear) and 842 (rbf). POLD1 - BLM shows low ranking of 1121 (laplace), 1118 (linear) and 1181 (rbf). POLG2 - BLM shows low ranking of 1509 (laplace), 849 (linear) and 1187 (rbf). POLQ - BLM shows low ranking of 464 (linear) and 144 (rbf). POLE2 - BLM shows low ranking of 413 (linear) and 317 (rbf). POLA1 - BLM shows low ranking of 9 (linear) and 63 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, POLB, POLD2 and POLE3 showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

The table 17 also shows rankings of POLR members w.r.t BLM. POLR2G - BLM shows low ranking of 771 (laplace) and 1375 (linear) POLR3K - BLM shows low ranking of 810 (laplace), 650 (linear) and 619 (rbf). POLR3E - BLM shows low ranking of 1384 (laplace), 1283 (linear) and 1508 (rbf). POLR1E - BLM shows low ranking of 662 (linear) and 1195 (rbf). POLR1B - BLM shows low ranking of 65 (linear) and 14 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, POLR2F, POLR2D, POLR3A, POLR1D, POLR2K and POLR1A showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following

RANKING POL-POLR FAMILY VS BLM							
RANKING OF POL FAMILY W.R.T BLM							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
POLA2 - BLM	759	1175	842	POLB - BLM	765	2047	2296
POLD1 - BLM	1121	1118	1181	POLG2 - BLM	1509	849	1187
POLQ - BLM	1728	464	144	POLE2 - BLM	1749	413	317
POLD2 - BLM	1906	2300	1366	POLE3 - BLM	2061	1967	2222
POLA1 - BLM	2570	9	63				
RANKING OF POLR FAMILY W.R.T BLM							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
POLR2F - BLM	352	2280	2168	POLR2D - BLM	490	2386	2380
POLR2G - BLM	771	1375	1594	POLR3K - BLM	810	650	619
POLR3A - BLM	1115	1706	2477	POLR1D - BLM	1266	2437	2712
POLR3E - BLM	1384	1283	1508	POLR2K - BLM	1701	2277	2548
POLR1A - BLM	2143	2248	438	POLR1E - BLM	2169	662	1195
POLR1B - BLM	2733	65	14				

Table 17: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between BLM VS POL-POLR members.

- influences - • POL members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > POL-A2/D1/G2/Q/E2/A1 and
- POLR members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > POLR-2G/3K/3E/1E/1B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

POL members w.r.t BLM

POL-A2/D1/G2/Q/E2/A1 BLM

POLR members w.r.t BLM

POLR-2G/3K/3E/1E/1B BLM

Table 18: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and POL-POLR members.

2.1.10. BLM - USP

Wu et al. [21] demonstrate the presence of USP37–BLM axis where USP37 interacts with BLM and deubiquitinates and stabilizes BLM, thereby sustaining the DNA damage response (DDR). They show that DNA DSB promotes ATM phosphorylation of USP37, which enhances the binding between USP37 and BLM. They further show that knockdown of USP37 increases BLM polyubiquitination, accelerates its proteolysis, and impairs its function in DNA damage response, thus leading to enhanced DNA damage and sensitization of breast cancer cells to DNA-damaging agents in both cell culture and in vivo mouse models. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, USP family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their

regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these USP members along with BLM.

Table 19 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 20 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 19. The table 19 shows rankings of USP members w.r.t BLM. USP28 - BLM shows low ranking of 223 (laplace) and 1193 (rbf). USP36 - BLM shows low ranking of 375 (laplace) and 851 (linear). USP13 - BLM shows low ranking of 288 (linear) and 435 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, USP10, USP1 and USP39 showed high ranking with BLM, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with BLM, before the drug treatment.

RANKING USP FAMILY VS BLM

RANKING OF USP FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
USP28 - BLM	223	2104	1193
USP36 - BLM	375	851	2221
USP10 - BLM	1527	1729	2740
USP13 - BLM	1836	288	435
USP1 - BLM	1965	1469	1727
USP39 - BLM	2281	1877	2207

Table 19: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between BLM VS USP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 19 graphically, with the following influences - • USP members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > USP-28/36/13.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

USP members w.r.t BLM	
USP-28/36/13	BLM

Table 20: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and USP members.

2.1.11. BLM - SMC

During *Caenorhabditis elegans* meiosis recombination, Hong et al. [22] show that the SMC-5/6 complex acts synergistically with HIM-6 (an ortholog of the human BLM). This concerted action of the SMC-5/6 complex and HIM-6/BLM is important for processing recombination intermediates, crossover regulation and bivalent maturation. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, SMC family members and BLM, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these SMC members along with BLM.

Table 21 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 22 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 21. The table 21 shows rankings of SMC members w.r.t BLM. SMC4 - BLM shows low ranking of 754 (laplace), 684 (linear) and 1210 (rbf). SMC1A - BLM shows low ranking of 1528 (laplace) and 1042 (rbf). SMC2 - BLM shows low ranking of 725 (linear) and 696 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING SMC FAMILY VS BLM			
RANKING OF SMC FAMILY W.R.T BLM			
	laplace	linear	rbf
SMC4 - BLM	754	684	1210
SMC1A - BLM	1528	2133	1042
SMC2 - BLM	2123	725	696

Table 21: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between BLM VS SMC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 21 graphically, with the following influences - • SMC members w.r.t BLM with BLM – > SMC-4/1A/2.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
SMC members w.r.t BLM	
SMC-4/1A/2	BLM

Table 22: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between BLM and SMC members.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic BLM 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of BLM-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [23].

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